

Supplemental Table 6. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between parity and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Parity measurements	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥ 20 years of age	11 561	Multiparous women (2+ pregnancies) had higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG); nulliparous women had higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG)	NS difference in odds of insufficient (vs adequate) GWG between women with parity of 0 and parity of 1	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity 2 Parity ≥ 3	No	S & NS
Bogaerts, A.	2012	Belgium	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in Flanders in 2009	54 022	Multiparous women had lower odds of excessive GWG and higher odds of insufficient GWG		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Caulfield, L. E.	1996	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and White women who delivered at John Hopkins Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics from 1987-89	3 870	Lower odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if parous (≥ 1)	NS effect of parity on odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG)	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity ≥ 2	No	S & NS
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Among Asian women: lower risk of insufficient GWG if primiparous and higher risk of excessive GWG if primiparous		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	<u>Underweight</u> : lower odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous - <u>Normal weight</u> : lower odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous (vs parous), while higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous - <u>Overweight</u> : higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous - <u>Obese</u> : lower odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous; higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous	NS effect of parity on excessive GWG in underweight group and on insufficient GWG in overweight group	Parity 0 Parity ≥ 1	No	S & NS
Gaillard, R.	2013	Netherlands	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 959	Lower odds of excessive GWG if multiparous		Nulliparous Multiparous	No	S
Groth, S. W.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	White and Black women aged 18-35 with a BMI between 18.5 and 34.9 kg/m ² who participated in a RCT from 2009-14	774	Multiparous women had lower GWG than primiparous women when all BMI groups analyzed together (true for both gene groups)	When divided by BMI, differences in GWG by parity did not remain significant (for all groups)	Primiparous Multiparous	No	S & NS

Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300	Significant differences in GWG adequacy according to parity (0, 1, 2, 3, 4+)		Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity 2 Parity 3 Parity ≥4	No	S
Holowko, N.	2015	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women with 2 pregnancies included in the Swedish Medical Birth Register and the Education Register from 1982-2010	163 352	Differing effects of education on adequacy of GWG (insufficient or excessive vs adequate) based on BMI and parity; in general: lower education was associated with higher odds of excessive GWG in underweight (1st pregnancy only) and normal weight women (1st and 2nd pregnancy); intermediate education reduced odds of insufficient GWG for underweight and normal weight women in 1st pregnancy; higher odds of insufficient GWG in overweight women with low/intermediate education (for 2nd pregnancy; 1st pregnancy: only associated with low education)	NS effect of education on GWG adequacy (odds of excessive or insufficient GWG, as compared to adequate) for obese women during pregnancy 1 or 2	Measured as an interaction variable for effect of education on adequacy of GWG	No	S [§] & NS [§]
Howie, L. D.	2003	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Women included in the 2000 US Natality File (excluding women from California, as GWG there is not collected)	2 796 805	Odds of excessive GWG (>40 lbs) higher in primiparous women		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Incollingo Rodriguez, A. C.	2019	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in the multi-site Community Child Health Network study who indicated that they experience everyday discrimination due to their weight or height	214	Primiparity negatively associated with excessive GWG	NS association between primiparity and total GWG	Primiparous Multiparous	No	S & NS
Khanolkar, A. R.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical record/birth certificate; IOM 2009	All women who gave birth in Washington State from 2006-08	181 948	Significant difference in adequacy of GWG according to parity (1, 2, 3 or more)		Parity 1 Parity 2 Parity ≥3	No	S
Koh, H.	2013	Singapore	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG guideline by Wong et al., 2000	All women who delivered at a specific hospital from Jan-Apr 2008 (approximately 30% of infants in Singapore are delivered at this hospital every year)	1 166		NS effect of parity on GWG adequacy (insufficient or excessive)	Nulliparous Multiparous	No	NS
Kominiarek, M. A.	2018b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Large multi-site study with random selection of women who gave birth at one of the sites from 2008-11	29 861	Significant differences in GWG adequacy (inadequate, adequate, excessive) according to parity		Nulliparous Multiparous	No	S

Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if multiparous (2 or 3+ births vs 1); lower odds of excessive GWG if multiparous		Parity 1 Parity 2 Parity ≥3	No	S
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619	Lower odds of excessive GWG if multiparous (vs primiparous)		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM (1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥15 years old	5 554	Significantly higher prevalence of excessive GWG with primiparity; higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in multiparous		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Naiqiso, S. L. S	2019	New Zealand	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in prenatal care with Counties Manukau Health from September 2004 - March 2016	604	Multiparous women (2 or 3+ births) had lower odds of excessive GWG (compared to nulliparous)	NS effect of parity on odds of insufficient GWG; NS effect of having had 1 previous birth vs no previous births on odds of excessive GWG	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity 2 Parity ≥3	No	S & NS
Ochsenbein-Kolble, N.	2007	Switzerland and	Cross-sectional	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	White, Asian, and Black women at the Obstetric Outpatient Department at Zurich University Hospital from January 1996 - February 2000	4 034	Among White women: parity had a significant effect on GWG (effect on other race/ethnicities not noted)		Continuous	No	S
Park, J. H.	2011	Korea	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified (no official guidelines in Korea)	Single-site study of women who gave birth at a university hospital from 2005-07	2 311	Insufficient GWG (<10 kg) significantly more prevalent in multiparous women		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Increased odds of insufficient GWG in parous women (1-2, or 3+ births vs 0); decreased odds of excessive GWG if parous (1-2 or 3+ births vs 0)		Parity 0 Parity 1-2 Parity ≥3	No	S
Platner, M. H.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in New York City from 2008-2012	515 148	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG based on parity (0 vs 1+)		Parity 0 Parity ≥1	No	S
Rosal, M. C.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study involving Non-Latina White and Latina women	571		NS effect of parity (0 vs 1, 2, 3+ births) on odds of excessive or insufficient GWG	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity 2 Parity ≥3	No	NS

Stogianni, A.	2019	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guidelines identified	Women with and without diabetes who were admitted to a specific hospital in Kronoberg from January 2009 - December 2012	280	Multiparity reduced odds of high GWG (categorized as GWG ≥ 8 kg) in women without diabetes	In women with diabetes: parity not associated with high GWG	First delivery Multiparous (≥ 2 deliveries)	No	S & NS
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥ 18 years old	250 857	Decreased odds of insufficient GWG if primiparous (vs multiparous); increased odds of excessive GWG if primiparous		Primiparous Multiparous	No	S
Wells, C. S.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-02 Colorado Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	4 528	Higher odds of insufficient GWG if parous (any previous live birth vs no previous live birth); lower odds of excessive GWG if parous		No previous live birth Any previous live births	No	S
Allison, K. C.	2012	USA	Cross-sectional	Medical records; IOM 2009	Black women ≥ 18 yrs of age receiving prenatal care at a university hospital for women on community-based insurance; all women had a BMI ≥ 25 kg/m ²	120		No correlation between GWG and parity	Continuous	Yes	NS
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents < 18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337		NS association between parity and GWG (compared adolescents gaining < 20 lbs to those gaining 20+ lbs)	Parity ≥ 1	Yes	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2008	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Hispanic (primarily Puerto Rican), low-income women receiving prenatal care at a public clinic from 2000-03	770	Lower risk of excessive GWG if parous (in multinomial logistic regression)	NS effect of parity on insufficient GWG (in multinomial logistic regression)	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity ≥ 2	Yes	S & NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276		NS difference in adequacy of GWG (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to parity (0, 1, or 2+)	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity ≥ 2	Yes	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293		Parity (0, 1 or 2+) was not associated with adequacy of GWG (insufficient, adequate, or excessive)	Parity 0 Parity 1 Parity ≥ 2	Yes	NS

Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) based on parity (no previous live birth vs one+ previous live births)	No previous live birth ≥1 previous live births	Yes	S
Fernandez, I. D.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Population registry of adolescents who gave birth in Upstate New York from 1996-2002	6 995	Significant differences in total GWG by parity (0, 1, or 2+ live births)	Parity 0 (nulliparous) Parity 1 (primiparous) Parity ≥2 (multiparous)	Yes	S
Hediger, M. L.	1990	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Low-income adolescents registered in the Camden County Adolescent Family Life program from 1982-87	1 419	Primigravidity contributed significantly to higher GWG in last half of pregnancy	Primigravid Multigravid	Yes	S
Herring, S. J.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Urban, low-income, primarily Black women seeking prenatal care at a university hospital from 2009-11	94	Nulliparity (vs. multiparity) was a significant predictor of excessive GWG	Nulliparous Multiparous	Yes	S
Hickey, C. A.	1992b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG evaluated as a percent of standard W/H (Rosso, 1985)	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women enrolled in prenatal care at two university-operated clinics	150	NS association between low GWG and parity	Not identified	Yes	NS
Hickey, C. A.	1997a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income, multiparous Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806	NS association between insufficient GWG and parity	Parity 1 Parity 2	Yes	NS
Hickey, C. A.	1992a	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Low-income, primarily Black, adolescents (<20 years) with 2 completed pregnancies from 1983-90	152	A significant decrease in weight gain in second pregnancy for older adolescents	NS difference in GWG between first and second pregnancies for younger adolescents	Yes	S & NS
Johnson, P. J.	2002	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Primarily low-income, urban women seeking prenatal care at a specific clinic from 1997-98	578	<u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories (insufficient, adequate, excessive):</u> significant difference by parity (1st birth vs 1+ previous birth; only significant for adults)	<u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories for adolescents only:</u> NS association with parity	Yes	S & NS

Meng, Y.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Black women seeking prenatal care at one of two clinics from 2008-11, all of whom were ≥18 years of age and enrolled in Medicaid and/or the Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children	55	Higher GWG associated with lower parity		Continuous	Yes	S
Nunnery, D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women attending a WIC clinic (for low-income women) in 2014 who were receiving WIC as a maternity client and were ≥18 years old	160		In multivariate regression: NS association between parity (primiparous vs multiparous) and odds of excessive GWG	Primiparous Multiparous	Yes	NS
Power, M. L.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with primarily White non-Hispanic women in rural counties in Pennsylvania who gave birth from 2006-15	18 217	Total GWG decreased as parity increased		Not identified	Yes	S
Ratan, B. M.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Low-income women with obesity who enrolled in prenatal care at a specific clinic in Houston, Texas from September 2013 August 2017; all women were receiving social assistance (CHIP Perinate or Medicaid)	772	Higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous (vs multiparous)	NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous (as compared to multiparous)	Nulliparous Multiparous	Yes	S & NS
Sangi-Haghpeykar, H.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Hispanic women who delivered at a specific hospital in Texas	282		NS difference in adequacy of GWG based on having previous pregnancies	Had a previous pregnancy Did not have a previous pregnancy	Yes	NS
Scholl, T. O.	1995	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Women age 12-29 with a low-income and a normal BMI; most women were Puerto Rican Hispanic or Black (data from Camden Study)	274	Excessive rate of GWG (as compared to low or moderate rate of GWG) significantly more prevalent in primiparous		Primiparous Multiparous	Yes	S
Schumacher, T. L.	2018	Australia	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Indigenous women, or women carrying an Indigenous child, who sought prenatal care at one of three sites in New South Wales	110	Multiparity associated with higher GWG		Nulliparous Multiparous	Yes	S

Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: positive association with primiparous (at any age vs multiparous at 20-29 yrs); negative association with being multiparous (only when younger than 20 or older than 29 yrs vs multiparous at 20-29 yrs) Multivariate logistic regression for insufficient GWG (<21 lbs for underweight/normal weight women, <10 lbs for overweight/obese women): for normal/underweight, decreased odds of insufficient GWG if primiparous (only if <20 or 20-29 yrs)	NS association between total GWG (for all women) and being multiparous at <20 yrs old or >29.1 yrs old NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG (for all women): multiparity at any age; specific to overweight/obese women: NS effect of being primiparous (any age); in underweight/normal weight women: NS effect of being primiparous (if >29 years old)	Primiparous Multiparous (Note: parity was examined jointly with age)	Yes	S & NS
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if primiparous (no previous live birth vs previous live birth); lower odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if primiparous		No previous live birth A previous live births	Yes	S